

Methylthymol Blue as a Reagent for Beryllium

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A method for the determination of beryllium (1–9 μg) with methylthymol blue (MTB) has been described. The method involves the formation of a red complex of Be–MTB at pH 5.0 ($\lambda_{\text{max}} = 500 \text{ m}\mu$). The colour reaction has a sensitivity of 0.00066 μg per sq. cm. and obeys Beer's Law over the range .04 to .36 ppm of beryllium. The present method is simple and rapid, and with a molar absorptivity of 13,250, it compares favourably with the most sensitive of the techniques used at present. The addition of a small amount of EDTA is effective in eliminating the interference of bivalent ions.

Methylthymol blue (MTB) has been extensively used as a chromogenic reagent and as a metallochromic indicator for metal ions. In earlier communications the authors have described the use of methylthymol blue (penta sodium salt) for the spectrophotometric determination of trace amounts of palladium¹, uranium (VI)², iron (II)³ and lead (II)⁴. During the investigations of the chromogenic properties of methylthymol blue⁵ it was observed that it yields a red complex with beryllium at pH 5.0, and the reaction is unaffected by the presence of conventional masking agents such as EDTA. This reaction has been further investigated and a simple and sensitive procedure has now been developed for the spectrophotometric determination of beryllium.

The red colour was found to be formed by the addition of a solution of beryllium perchlorate to the reagent, buffered within pH range 4–7, but a pH range between 5.0 and 5.5 was found to be optimal for colour development.

Initially an acetate buffer was used to maintain the pH within this optimal range, but the observed absorbance was always found to be lower than that obtained with the hexamethylene tetramine perchloric acid buffer. This may be due to the fact that acetate forms a complex with beryllium, rendering it ionically unavailable. The buffer system, hexamethylene tetramineperchloric acid was employed, which has a great buffering capacity in the pH range from 4 to 7. The amount of the buffer had no effect on the colour intensity of the complex provided that more than 2.5 ml. of the said solution was used.

It was observed that a 12 fold excess of the reagent was required for maximal absorbance values. As a compromise between sensitivity and absorbance by the blank solution 10 ml of a $1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ reagent solution was used.

1. K. C. Srivastava and S. K. Banerji, unpublished data.
2. Idem, *Microchem. J.*, 1968, **13**, 699.
3. Idem, *ibid.*, 1968, **13**, 621.
4. Idem, *Chim. Anal.*, 1969, **51**, 28.
5. Idem, *Chem. Age India*, 1969, **20**, 606.

The intensity of the colour increases with rise in temperature, the maximum colour development is attained within 20 min when the mixture is heated to 80° in a water bath. The absorbance remains constant for atleast 8 hr after this at pH 5.0. The order of addition of the reagents was found to be of no significance.

Fig. 1 shows the absorption curve of methylthymol blue and its beryllium complex. The absorption curve of the beryllium complex obtained with a reagent blank as reference has a absorption maximum at 500 m μ . All measurements were made at 500 m μ .

Fig. 1.

fig. 1 : Absorption curves of methylthymol blue and its beryllium complex at pH 5.0

Be : 9 μ g; MTB 4.0×10^{-4} M

A : MTB vs. water

B : Be-MTB+MTB vs. water.

C : Be-MTB+MTB vs. a reagent blank.

The analytical potentiality of the procedure was checked against the Lambert-Beer Law performance of the colour system (Fig. 2) and calibration curves showed linearity in the range 0.9 to 9 μ g of beryllium with net molar absorptivity ϵ 500 m μ = 13,250. The sensitivity of the reaction as expressed by sandell's notation⁶ is .00066 μ g of beryllium per cm².

6. E. B. Sandell, "The Colorimetric Determination of Traces of Metals", Interscience Publishers, New York, 1950, pp. 49.

An examination of the data presented in Table I shows that MTB is considerably more sensitive than some conventional colorimetric reagents and the proposed procedure is more selective than most others.

Fig. 2.

Fig. 2 : Calibration curve
MTB $4.0 \times 10^{-4} M$
pH 5.0, 500 m μ .

TABLE I

Sensitivity of Colorimetric reagents for beryllium

Reagent	Maximal absorption m μ	Sensitivity index	Reference
Methylthymol blue	500	0.00066	
Acetylacetone	295	0.001	7, 8
Aurintricarboxylic acid	515	0.01	9, 10
Chrome Azurol S	575	0.0004	11
Eriochrome Cyanine R	512	0.004	12
Fast sulfon Black F	630	0.001	13
8-Hydroxyquinaldine	380	0.01	7, 14
Alkannin and naphthazarin	—	0.005	15
<i>p</i> -Nitrobenzene azoarcinol	525	0.05	7, 16
Naphthochrome Green G	—	0.01	7, 10, 17
2-phenoxyquinizarin-3,4-disulfonic acid (dipotassium salt)	550	0.01	18
Quinizarin-2-sulfonic acid	575	0.005	19
Xylenol orange	495	0.0006	20
Sodium chlorophenol azo, 1,8-dihydroxy naphthalene 3,6-disulfonate	610	0.0008	21

7. E. B. Sandell, "Colorimetric Determination of Traces of Metals" 3rd ed., Interscience Publishers, Inc., New York, 1959, pp. 304-324.

Composition of beryllium methylthymol blue complex : The composition of the beryllium methylthymol blue complex was determined by two methods, the method of continuous variations,²² and the mole-ratio method²³. The results indicate that beryllium forms a 1 : 1 complex with MTB at pH 5.0. The conditional stability constant of the complex obtained by calculations based on the mole-ratio data was found to be 7.7×10^5 at $30 \pm 0.5^\circ$.

Effect of other ions : Table II indicates the effect of anions on the determination of beryllium. Chloride, nitrate and sulfate ions do not interfere, even when present in a high concentration. Oxalate and phosphate ions give negative errors at low concentrations. Fluoride and citrate ions bleach the colour of the complex even when less than 2μ mol. is present. Nitrilotriacetic acid (NTA) and EDTA, which form stable complexes with many other metal ions to decompose the corresponding methylthymol blue complexes, have almost no influence on the complex formation between beryllium and methylthymol blue unless large amounts are added. Therefore, NTA and EDTA can be used as masking agents to prevent the interference of other heavy metals. EDTA has been used as a masking agent in several methods of beryllium determination²⁴⁻²⁷ and recently Owens and Yoe²⁸ used the calcium-EDTA complex as a sequestering agent in the spectrophotometric determination of beryllium.

The effect of cations : Methylthymol blue is a selective reagent for certain cations when it is used in a relatively strong acid medium. However, in a slightly acid medium it reacts with many metal cations to give blue, red or reddish violet complexes, indicating that

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27. P. W. West and P. R. Mohilner, *ibid.*, 1962, **34**, 558.
28. E. G. Owens, II and J. H. Yoe, *Anal. Chem.*, 1960, **32**, 1345.

TABLE II

The effect of anions and complexing agents. Beryllium taken : 9 μ g.

Anion or Complexing agent, added. μ mol.	Beryllium found μ g	Deviation μ g
Cl ⁻	100	\pm 0.0
	250	+ 0.1
F ⁻	2	- 0.3
	5	- 2.8
NO ₃ ⁻	100	\pm 0.0
	250	\pm 0.0
SO ₄ ²⁻	100	+ 0.2
	200	\pm 0.0
C ₂ O ₄ ²⁻	5	- 0.5
	20	- 1.3
C ₄ H ₄ O ₆ ²⁻	10	\pm 0.0
	25	- 0.1
PO ₄ ³⁻	5	- 1.0
	10	- 1.1
C ₆ H ₅ O ₇ ³⁻	2	- 1.2
	5	- 2.6
NTA	1	\pm 0.0
	5	- 0.2
EDTA	0.5	\pm 0.0
	2.5	- 0.2

a suitable masking agent must be used to increase the selectivity. Disodium salt of EDTA was chosen for this reason. The common bivalent ions can be effectively masked by EDTA as shown in Table III. The following cationic interference could not be masked : aluminium, bismuth, thorium and zirconium.

DISCUSSION

With an extinction coefficient of 13,250 the technique compares favourably with those at present in use for the spectrophotometric determination of beryllium. It has been found that MTB is a better reagent for beryllium than eriochrome cyanine R, 2 phenoxyquini-Zarin 3,4 sulfonic acid, aurin tricarboxylic acid; and sodium *p*-chlorophenol-azo-1,8-dihydroxy naphthalene 3,6-disulphonate. In principle this method offers considerable advantage however, in that the method is readily reproducible, while still preserving a high degree of selectivity.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of calibration curve—Reagents :

10⁻³ M Beryllium perchlorate : Prepared by dilution of standardised 5 \times 10⁻² M beryllium perchlorate.

TABLE III

Masking effect of EDTA

Beryllium taken : 9.0 μg ; Cations added : each 2.0 μmol ; EDTA added : 2.5 μmol .

Cation	Beryllium found μg	Deviation μg
Mg ²⁺	8.8	- 0.2
Zn ²⁺	8.9	- 0.1
Cd ²⁺	9.0	\pm 0.0
Hg ²⁺	8.9	- 0.1
Cu ²⁺	8.8	- 0.2
Pb ²⁺	8.7	- 0.3
Mn ²⁺	8.8	- 0.2
Pd ²⁺	8.8	- 0.2
Co ²⁺	9.0	\pm 0.0
Fe ³⁺	9.1	+ 0.1
Bi ³⁺	9.6	+ 0.6
La ³⁺	9.3	+ 0.3

10⁻³ M methylthymol blue solution : Prepared by dissolving the Eastman MTB reagent (penta sodium salt) in distilled water. This solution is best prepared every 3 days.

Buffer solution : A hexamine-perchloric acid mixture was prepared by dissolving 3.5 g of hexamine in 100 ml of distilled water and by adding perchloric acid solution in order to bring the pH to a desired value.

Apparatus : Hilger Uvispek spectrophotometer with 1 cm. cuvettes.

Procedure : An aliquot of the standard beryllium solution was introduced in a 25 ml volumetric flask. 5 ml of a pH 5.0 buffer, 10 ml of a 1 \times 10⁻³ M methylthymol blues olution and then a small amount of water were added to make the solution about 20 ml. The solution was heated in a water bath at 80° for about 20 min, cooled with running water, diluted with water and made up. The resulting solution was kept for about 30 min in a thermostat at 30 \pm 0.5°. The absorbance of the solution was measured against a reagent blank at 500 m μ .

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